

Preparation and Characterisation of Phenoxides of Tellurium(IV)

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Compounds of composition $\text{TeCl}_{4-n}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5)_n$ ($n=1-4$) have been prepared by the reaction of tellurium(IV) chloride and trimethylsilylphenoxide. Analytical data, molar conductance, cryoscopic molecular weight determinations and infrared spectral data have been helpful to elucidate their structures. Lewis acid character of compounds of composition $\text{TeCl}_3(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5)$ and $\text{TeCl}_2(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5)_2$ have been established by isolating some addition compounds with organic tertiary bases. $\text{Te}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5)_4$ appears to behave as a solvo-acid in phenol in the presence of alkali metal phenoxides and as a phenoxide ion donor in the presence of $\text{Ti}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5)_4$.

ALTHOUGH alkoxide derivatives of sulphur, selenium and tellurium are known¹, but their corresponding phenoxy derivatives has not been reported so far. In one of the reports² on the reactions of tellurium(IV) chloride with phenols it was described that despite the acidic nature of the hydroxyl proton, phenol undergoes a Friedel-Crafts type condensation reaction with tellurium tetrachloride involving the attack by TeCl_3^+ unit on the position *para* to the hydroxyl group in the aromatic ring. It is therefore of our interest to isolate and characterise phenoxides of tellurium(IV). We report herein the preparation of phenoxides of tellurium(IV) by the reaction of tellurium(IV) chloride with trimethylsilylphenoxide.

Experimental

Tellurium(IV) chloride (Reidel) was used as such. Xylene (B.D.H.) was distilled twice over P_2O_5 and sodium wire and was finally dried (molecular sieves) before use. Trimethylsilylphenoxide and alkali metal phenoxides were prepared by reported method.

Preparation of compounds: Compounds of composition $\text{TeCl}_3(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5)$ (1), $\text{TeCl}_2(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5)_2$ (2), $\text{TeCl}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5)_3$ (3) and $\text{Te}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5)_4$ (4) were prepared by refluxing tellurium(IV) chloride and trimethylsilylphenoxide in the exact predetermined 1 : 1, 1 : 2, 1 : 3 and slightly excess than 1 : 4 molar ratios in xylene for 20–24 h. Complexes 1–3 were separated as insoluble residue whereas 4 was separated from the clear solution of the reactants by the addition of petroleum ether. These were filtered, washed with petroleum ether and dried under reduced pressure.

Addition compounds of composition, $\text{TeCl}_{4-n}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5)_n \cdot 2\text{L}$ and $\text{TeCl}_{4-n}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5)_n \cdot \text{B}$ ($n=1, 2$) were prepared by stirring the two components in 1 : 2 molar ratio in xylene for about 48 h.

Tellurium was estimated as metal and chlorine by Volhard's method. Determination of molar con-

ductance values and conductometric titrations were performed on an Elico CM-82T conductivity bridge. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 337 and 621 spectrometers. Molecular weights were determined cryoscopically in nitrobenzene.

Results and Discussion

The interaction of tellurium(IV) chloride with $\text{Me}_3\text{Si}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5)$ in xylene permits the formation of tellurium-oxygen bond in different phenoxy derivatives and trimethylsilylphenoxide in accordance with the equation,

The compounds are brown or reddish brown solids with fairly high melting points, and insoluble in non-polar organic solvents but soluble in more polar solvents. Molar conductance values of the compounds in nitrobenzene ($10^{-3} M$) were in the range $1.5-9.5 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$ suggesting their non-electrolytic nature. Molecular weight determination of $\text{TeCl}_3(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5)$, $\text{TeCl}_2(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5)_2$ and $\text{TeCl}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5)_3$ suggest that they are dimeric while $\text{Te}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5)_4$ exists as monomer (Table 1).

To gain an insight into the formation of tellurium-oxygen bond in the compounds, ir spectra have provided the useful information. The most important and significant band in the region $560-580 \text{cm}^{-1}$ (not present in the ligand) has been assigned to $\nu_{\text{Te-O}}$ mode³. In the case of $\text{TeCl}_3(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5)$, $\text{TeCl}_2(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5)_2$ and $\text{TeCl}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5)_3$ bands at $480-500 \text{cm}^{-1}$ may be assigned to bridging $\text{Te} \begin{array}{c} \diagup \text{O} \diagdown \\ \text{---} \end{array} \text{Te}$ mode. No such band was observed in $\text{Te}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5)_4$. Apart from these bands, sharp bands at $350-370 \text{cm}^{-1}$ may be assigned to $\nu_{\text{Te-Cl}}$ mode⁴.

With a limited information, based upon infrared data and molecular weight measurements, a dimeric structure for $\text{TeCl}_3(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5)$, $\text{TeCl}_2(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5)_2$ and

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, PHYSICAL AND PRINCIPAL IR SPECTRAL DATA OF PHENOXIDES OF TELLURIUM(IV)

Compd.	Colour	M.p. °C	Analysis % :		ν_{\max}			
			Found/	(Calcd.)	Te-O	Te-O-Te	Te-Cl	Te-N
Te(OC ₆ H ₅) ₄	Reddish brown	225	25.58 (25.54)	—	580	—	—	—
TeCl(OC ₆ H ₅) ₃	Dark brown	215	28.82 (28.86)	8.07 (8.02)	582	485	356	—
TeCl ₂ (OC ₆ H ₅) ₂	Brown	219d	33.19 (33.17)	18.43 (18.46)	588	482	368	—
TeCl ₃ (OC ₆ H ₅)	Brown	208d	38.97 (39.00)	32.49 (32.55)	592	480	372	—
TeCl ₂ (OC ₆ H ₅) ₂ ·py	Brown	182d	26.32 (26.30)	21.91 (21.95)	572	—	371	279
TeCl ₂ (OC ₆ H ₅) ₂ ·bipy	Brown	193d	26.44 (26.41)	22.03 (22.04)	570	—	372	274
TeCl ₂ (OC ₆ H ₅) ₂ ·phen	Light brown	176	25.19 (25.16)	21.08 (21.00)	574	—	362	278
TeCl ₂ (OC ₆ H ₅) ₂ ·phenO ₂	Brown	184	21.34 (21.37)	17.88 (17.85)	565	—	378	—
TeCl ₂ (OC ₆ H ₅) ₂ ·bipyO ₂	Light brown	171d	24.74 (24.77)	20.68 (20.67)	542	—	375	—
TeCl ₂ (OC ₆ H ₅) ₂ ·2py	Brown	158	23.48 (23.51)	13.07 (13.08)	562	—	368	272
TeCl ₂ (OC ₆ H ₅) ₂ ·bipy	Brown	200	23.56 (23.60)	13.19 (13.13)	571	—	364	270
TeCl ₂ (OC ₆ H ₅) ₂ ·phen	Brown	188d	20.83 (20.82)	12.59 (12.57)	570	—	365	275
TeCl ₂ (OC ₆ H ₅) ₂ ·phenO ₂	Brown	—	21.4 (21.4)	11.9 (11.9)	572	—	380	—
TeCl ₂ (OC ₆ H ₅) ₂ ·bipyO ₂	Brown	157	22.3 (22.2)	12.4 (12.4)	572	—	375	—

TeCl(OC₆H₅)₃ and a monomeric structure for Te(OC₆H₅)₄ may be proposed.

Lewis acid character of these compounds has been established by isolating their addition compounds with both monodentate (L) and bidentate (B) ligands. Reactions of TeCl₃(OC₆H₅) and TeCl₂(OC₆H₅)₂ with various bases are exothermic and form compounds of composition TeCl_{4-n}(OC₆H₅)_n·2L and TeCl_{4-n}(OC₆H₅)_n·B (n=1, 2) as evidenced by elemental analysis (Table 1). Molar conductance and molecular weight determinations of these adducts suggest that all are non-ionic solids in solution and monomeric. Coordination of the ligands to the central metal of the compounds has been confirmed from the trends of the shifts of $\nu_{C=O}$, $\nu_{C=N}$ and $\delta(N-O)$ which are in agreement with the earlier reports of the adducts of other Lewis acids⁵. The new bands at 270–280 cm⁻¹ in these adducts may be assigned to ν_{Te-N} modes⁶. The bands due to

bridging Te-O-Te modes are not present in any of the adducts suggesting that adduct formation takes place by the rupture of phenoxy bridging followed by coordination of the ligand leading to stable hexacoordinated adducts. Similar observations have been made earlier also in the case of tellurium(IV) naphthoxides⁷.

Solvo-acid character of Te(OC₆H₅)₄ has been observed by carrying out conductometric titrations of the compound against sodium and potassium phenoxides in phenol at 50 ± 0.1°. The conductance-composition curves show two sharp breaks at

MOC₆H₅/Te(OC₆H₅)₄ (M=Na or K) molar ratios of 1 : 1 and 2 : 1 which may be due to the formation of the compounds of the type M[Te(OC₆H₅)₅] and M₂[Te(OC₆H₅)₆].

Similar type of ionic compounds have been postulated earlier in case of the reactions of Ti(OC₆H₅)₄ with alkali metal phenoxides⁸.

Conductometric titrations of Te(OC₆H₅)₄ against Ti(OC₆H₅)₄ in phenol at 50 ± 0.1° however illustrate that Te(OC₆H₅)₄ is a solvo-base. The conductance-composition curve which shows sharp breaks at the Ti(OC₆H₅)₄/Te(OC₆H₅)₄ molar ratios of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 may correspond to the compounds of composition [Te(OC₆H₅)₃] [Ti(OC₆H₅)₅] and [Te(OC₆H₅)₃]₂ [Ti(OC₆H₅)₆] in terms of the reactions,

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